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WP3 – Personalized Medicine

D3.2 First Report on the Implementation of the Analytical Pipeline for Personalized Medicine

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DEFINITIONS

Participants of the EHDEN Consortium are referred to herein according to the following codes:

EMC	Erasmus Universitair Medisch Centrum Rotterdam- The Netherlands (Project Coordinator)
Synapse	Synapse Research Management Partners S.L. - Spain
UOXF	The Chancellor, Masters and Scholars of the University of Oxford - United Kingdom
UTARTU	Tartu Ulikool - Estonia
UAVR	Universidade de Aveiro – Portugal
The Hyve	The Hyve BV – the Netherlands
Odysseus	Odysseus Data Services SRO – Czech Republic
EPF	Forum Europeen des Patients (FPE) - Luxembourg
NICE	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence – United Kingdom
UMC	Stiftelsen WHO Collaborating Centre for International Drug Monitoring - Sweden
ICHOM	International Consortium for Health Outcomes measurement LTD - United Kingdom
Janssen	Janssen Pharmaceutica NV - Belgium (Project Lead)
Pfizer	Pfizer Limited – United Kingdom
Abbvie	AbbVie Inc - United States
IRIS	Institut De Recherches Internationales Servier - France
SARD	Sanofi Aventis Recherche & Developpement - France
Bayer	Bayer Aktiengesellschaft - Germany
Lilly	Eli Lilly and Company Limited – United Kingdom
AZ	AstraZeneca AB - Sweden
Novartis	Novartis Pharma AG - Switzerland
UCB	UCB Biopharma SPRL - Belgium
Celgene	Celgene Management SARL - Switzerland

Grant agreement	The agreement signed between the beneficiaries and the IMI JU for the undertaking of the EHDEN project (806968).
Project	The sum of all activities carried out in the framework of the Grant Agreement.
Consortium	The EHDEN Consortium, comprising the above-mentioned legal entities.
Consortium agreement	Agreement concluded amongst EHDEN participants for the implementation of the Grant Agreement. Such an agreement shall not affect the parties' obligations to the Community and/or to one another arising from the Grant Agreement.

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

There are large opportunities to use the massive amount of observational data in Europe for personalized decision-making. However, the lack of inter-operability of the data sources makes this a challenging task. The differences in structure (syntactic inter-operability) and terminologies systems (semantic inter-operability) make the development of standardized analytical pipelines cumbersome. The European Health Data and Evidence Network (EHDEN) project is addressing this by standardizing a large amount of European data sources to the OMOP Common Data Model (CDM). The goal of WP3 “Personalized Medicine” is to establish a standardized process to enable personalized decision-making that can be utilized for multiple outcomes of interest and can be applied to observational healthcare data from any patient subpopulation.

This first report introduces the analytical pipelines for Patient-Level Prediction and Population-Level Effect Estimation that are being developed by the Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics (OHDSI) community. This work includes large contributions of EHDEN consortium members. Furthermore, we discuss our development of a pipeline for Risk Stratified Effect Estimation to assess heterogeneity of treatment effect.

The analytical pipelines have already been applied successfully in EHDEN in study-a-thons that try to answer important clinical questions in a short timeframe with a dedicated team of clinicians and data scientists.

This work falls under Task 3.2. “Development of an integrated patient-level prediction pipeline (M6-M60) and Task 3.3 “Development of an integrated risk-effect estimation pipeline (M6-M60).

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1. INTRODUCTION

The ultimate ambition of EHDEN is to enable a learning healthcare system by removing obstacles that at present prevent the exploitation of existing data, and by providing state-of-the-art analytical procedures and capabilities. We want to create an environment that allows a research community to utilize the ever-increasing amounts of data and that supports practitioners to translate resulting findings to better care. By establishing a high-quality European data network of patient records standardized to the same data structure and mapped to common standard vocabularies, we aim to create opportunities to move to large-scale analyses in a fully transparent and reproducible ecosystem. The strongly improved interoperability will enable the much faster data assessment that is needed to respond quickly to the continuously changing healthcare system. This will improve patient access to effective and innovative medicines and facilitate learning healthcare systems that can improve clinical decision-making and make healthcare delivery more efficient and personalized.

In our work in the personalized medicine domain, we distinguish two complimentary scientific tasks:

- 1) **Patient-Level Prediction (PLP)** tries to answer the question “What will happen to me?”. Based on the collected patient health histories in the database, we want to make patient-level predictions about future health events. To build these models we search for predictors that are correlated with the outcome, i.e. we perform inference. The PLP pipeline will be discussed in section 2.
- 2) **Population-Level effect estimation (PLE)** on the other hand tries to answer the question “What are causal effects?”. We want to make causal inference about the effects of healthcare interventions. For example, if we decide to take some treatment, how does that change what happens to us in the future. The causal questions can be best assessed using a fully randomized treatment assignment experiment. However, in observational data we can approximate this by predicting treatment assignment (propensity scores). The PLE pipeline will be discussed in section 3.

It is important to understand the difference between inference (prediction) and causal inference (effect estimation). Correlation does not mean there is a causal relationship that could have impact on treatment choice. For example, diabetic drug use might be a strong predictor for myocardial infarction (MI) because diabetes is a strong risk factor for MI. However, that does not mean that stopping the diabetic drugs will prevent MI! The PLP analytical pipeline implements best practices for the development and validation of prediction models on the OMOP CDM.

Both the Patient-Level Prediction framework and the Population-Level Effect estimation pipelines are described in detail in chapters in the new book the OHDSI Community has produced called “The Book of OHDSI” (<http://book.ohdsi.org>). During the first year of EHDEN, our partners EMC and JANSSEN have continued to lead the development of the PLP pipeline and have been responsible for the chapter on Patient-Level Prediction. JANSSEN has led the development of the pipeline for population-level effect estimation and has written the corresponding chapter together with other OHDSI collaborators. In this deliverable we highlight the important parts of both chapters to obtain a basic understanding of these very powerful analytical pipelines. Where necessary we refer to the book and R package vignettes for additional details.

Finally, our WP3 team has made considerable progress in the development of an analytical pipeline for the assessment of Heterogeneity of Treatment Effect (HTE) by combining the PLP and PLE functionality. The goal here is to understand if the benefit risk ratio may be different for patients that have a higher or lower baseline risk of the outcome. This new tool will be discussed in more detail in section 4.

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2. PATIENT-LEVEL PREDICTION

For a full explanation of the Patient-Level Prediction pipeline we refer to the Book-Of-OHDSI Chapter 13 “Patient-Level Prediction” led by Peter Rijnbeek (EMC), and Jenna Reys (JANSSEN) and the R-Package page that contains video instructions and more in depth documentation of more advanced functionality: <https://ohdsi.github.io/PatientLevelPrediction/>

Clinical decision making is a complicated task in which the clinician has to infer a diagnosis or treatment pathway based on the available medical history of the patient and the current clinical guidelines. Clinical prediction models have been developed to support this decision-making process and are used in clinical practice in a wide spectrum of specialties. These models predict a diagnostic or prognostic outcome based on a combination of patient characteristics, e.g. demographic information, disease history, and treatment history.

The number of publications describing clinical prediction models has increased strongly over the last 10 years. Most currently-used models are estimated using small datasets and consider only a small set of patient characteristics. This low sample size, and thus low statistical power, forces the data analyst to make strong modelling assumptions. The selection of the limited set of patient characteristics is strongly guided by the expert knowledge at hand. This contrasts sharply with the reality of modern medicine wherein patients generate a rich digital trail, which is well beyond the power of any medical practitioner to fully assimilate. Presently, health care is generating a huge amount of patient-specific information stored in Electronic Health Records (EHRs). This includes structured data in the form of diagnosis, medication, laboratory test results, and unstructured data contained in clinical narratives. It is unknown how much predictive accuracy can be gained by leveraging the large amount of data originating from the complete EHR of a patient.

Advances in machine learning for large dataset analysis have led to increased interest in applying patient-level prediction on this type of data. However, many published efforts in patient-level prediction do not follow the model development guidelines, fail to perform extensive external validation, or provide insufficient model details which limits the ability of independent researchers to reproduce the models and perform external validation. This makes it hard to fairly evaluate the predictive performance of the models and reduces the likelihood of the model being used appropriately in clinical practice. To improve standards, several papers have been written detailing guidelines for best practices in developing and reporting prediction models. For example, the Transparent Reporting of a multivariable prediction model for Individual Prognosis Or Diagnosis (TRIPOD) statement¹ provides clear recommendations for reporting prediction model development and validation and addresses some of the concerns related to transparency.

Massive-scale, patient-specific predictive modelling has become reality due to OHDSI, where the common data model (CDM) allows for uniform and transparent analysis at an unprecedented scale. The growing network of databases standardized to the CDM enables external validation of models in different healthcare settings on a global scale. We believe this provides immediate opportunity to serve large communities of patients who are in most need of improved quality of care. Such models can inform truly personalized medical care, leading hopefully to sharply improved patient outcomes.

In the next sections we describe the standardized framework for patient-level prediction (1), and discuss the PatientLevelPrediction R package that implements established best practices for development and validation. We start with providing some theory behind the development and evaluation of patient-level

prediction. We then discuss an example prediction problem and provide insight in its definition, implementation and execution. Finally, we discuss the use of Shiny applications for the dissemination of study results.

2.1 The Prediction Problem

Figure 1: The prediction problem.

Figure 1, illustrates the prediction problem we address. Among a population at risk, we aim to predict which patients at a defined moment in time ($t = 0$) will experience some outcome during a time-at-risk. Prediction is done using only information about the patients in an observation window prior to that moment in time.

As shown in Table 1, to define a prediction problem we have to define $t=0$ by a target cohort, the outcome we like to predict by an outcome cohort, and the time-at-risk. We define the standard prediction question as:

Among [target cohort definition], who will go on to have [outcome cohort definition] within [time-at-risk period]?

Furthermore, we have to make design choices for the model we like to develop and determine the observational datasets to perform internal and external validation.

Table 1: Main design choices in a prediction design

Choice	Description
Target cohort	How do we define the cohort of persons for whom we wish to predict?
Outcome cohort	How do we define the outcome we want to predict?
Time-at-risk	In which time window relative to $t=0$ do we want to make the prediction?
Model	What algorithms do we want to use, and which potential predictor variables do we include?

This conceptual framework works for all types of prediction problems, for example:

Disease onset and progression

- **Structure:** Among patients who are newly diagnosed with *[a disease]*, who will go on to have *[another disease or complication]* within *[time horizon from diagnosis]*?
- **Example:** Among newly diagnosed atrial fibrillation patients, who will go on to have ischemic stroke in the next three years?

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Treatment choice

- **Structure:** Among patients with *[indicated disease]* who are treated with either *[treatment 1]* or *[treatment 2]*, which patients were treated with *[treatment 1]*?
- **Example:** Among patients with atrial fibrillation who took either warfarin or rivaroxaban, which patients get warfarin? (e.g. for a propensity model)

Treatment response

- **Structure:** Among new users of *[a treatment]*, who will experience *[some effect]* in *[time window]* ?
- **Example:** Which patients with diabetes who start on a statin develop an acute cardiovascular event in 3 years from treatment initiation?

Treatment safety

- **Structure:** Among new users of *[a treatment]*, who will experience *[adverse event]* in *[time window]*?
- **Example:** Among new users of warfarin, who will have a gastrointestinal bleed in one year?

Treatment adherence

- **Structure:** Among new users of *[a treatment]*, who will achieve *[adherence metric]* at *[time window]*?
- **Example:** Which patients with diabetes who start on metformin will achieve $\geq 80\%$ proportion of days covered at one year?

2.2 Data Extraction

When creating a predictive model we use a process known as supervised learning, a form of machine learning that infers the relationship between the covariates and the outcome status based on a labelled set of examples. Therefore, we need methods to extract the covariates from the CDM for the persons in the target cohort and we need to obtain their outcome labels.

The **covariates** (also referred to as “predictors”, “features” or “independent variables”) describe the characteristics of the patients. Covariates can include age, gender, presence of specific conditions and exposure codes in a patient’s record, etc. Covariates are typically constructed using the FeatureExtraction package, described in more detail in Chapter 11 of the Book of OHDSI. For prediction we can only use data prior to (and on) the date the person enters the target cohort. This date we will call the *indexdate*.

We also need to obtain the **outcome status** (also referred to as the “labels” or “classes”) of all the patients during the time-at-risk. If the outcome occurs within the time-at-risk, the outcome status is defined as “positive.”

2.2 Fitting the Model

When fitting a prediction model we are trying to learn the relationship between the covariates and the observed outcome status from labelled examples. Suppose we only have two covariates, systolic and diastolic blood pressure, then we can represent each patient as a plot in two-dimensional space as shown in Figure 2. In this figure the shape of the data point corresponds to the patient’s outcome status (e.g. stroke).

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A supervised learning model will try to find a decision boundary that optimally separates the two outcome classes. Different supervised learning techniques lead to different decision boundaries and there are often hyper-parameters that can impact the complexity of the decision boundary.

In Figure 2, we can see three different decision boundaries. The boundaries are used to infer the outcome status of any new data point. If a new data point falls into the shaded area then the model will predict “has outcome”, otherwise it will predict “no outcome”. Ideally a decision boundary should perfectly partition the two classes. However, there is a risk that too complex models “overfit” to the data. This can negatively impact the generalizability of the model to unseen data. For example, if the data contains noise, with mislabelled or incorrectly positioned data points, we would not want to fit our model to that noise. We therefore may prefer to define a decision boundary that does not perfectly discriminate in our training data but captures the “real” complexity. Techniques such as regularization aim to maximize model performance while minimizing complexity.

Figure 2: Decision boundary.

Each supervised learning algorithm has a different way to learn the decision boundary and it is not straightforward which algorithm will work best on your data. As the No Free Lunch theorem states not one algorithm is always going to outperform the others on all prediction problems. Therefore, we recommend trying multiple supervised learning algorithms with various hyper-parameter settings when developing patient-level prediction models. A large number of machine learning algorithms are available in the PatientLevelPrediction package, such as Regularized Logistic Regression, Gradient Boosting Machines, Random Forest, and Deep Learning.

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2.3 Evaluating Prediction Models

We can evaluate a prediction model by measuring the agreement between the model's prediction and observed outcome status, which means we need data where the outcome status is known.

We distinguish between:

- **Internal validation:** Using different sets of data extracted from the same database to develop and evaluate the model.
- **External validation:** Developing the model in one database, and evaluating in another database.

There are two ways implemented to perform **internal validation**:

- 1) A **holdout set** approach splits the labelled data into two independent sets: a train set and a test set (the hold out set). The train set is used to learn the model and the test set is used to evaluate it. We can simply divide our patients randomly into a train and test set, or we may choose to:
 - Split the data based on time (temporal validation), for example training on data before a specific date, and evaluating on data after that date. This may inform us on whether our model generalizes to different time periods.
 - Split the data based on geographic location (spatial validation).
- 2) **Cross validation** is useful when the data are limited. The data is split into n equally- sized sets, where n needs to be prespecified (e.g. $n = 10$). For each of these sets a model is trained on all data except the data in that set and used to generate predictions for the hold-out set. In this way, all data is used once to evaluate the model-building algorithm. In the patient-level prediction framework we use cross validation to pick the optimal hyper-parameters.

External validation aims to assess model performance on data from another database, i.e. out- side of the settings it was developed in. This measure of model transportability is important because we want to apply our models not only on the database it was trained on. Different databases may represent different patient populations, different healthcare systems and different data-capture processes. We believe that the external validation of prediction models on a large set of databases is a crucial step in model acceptance and implementation in clinical practice.

Following the TRIPOD statement (2), the models should be evaluated using discrimination and calibration measures:

Discrimination

Discrimination is the ability to assign a higher risk to patients who will experience the out- come during the time at risk. The Receiver Operating Characteristics (ROC) curve is created by plotting $1 - \text{specificity}$ on the x-axis and sensitivity on the y-axis at all possible thresh- olds. The area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC) gives an overall measure of discrimination where a value of 0.5 corresponds to randomly assigning the risk and a value of 1 means perfect discrimination. Most published prediction models obtain AUCs between 0.6-0.8. The AUC provides a way to determine how different the predicted risk distributions are between the patients who experience the outcome during the time at risk and those who do not. If the AUC is high, then the distributions will be mostly disjointed, whereas when there is a lot of overlap, the AUC will be closer to 0.5, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: How the ROC plots are linked to discrimination. If the two classes have similar distributions of predicted risk, the ROC will be close to the diagonal, with AUC close to 0.5.

Calibration

Calibration is the ability of the model to assign the correct risk. For example, if the model assigned one hundred patients a risk of 10% then ten of the patients should experience the outcome during the time at risk. If the model assigned 100 patients a risk of 80% then eighty of the patients should experience the outcome during the time at risk. The calibration is generally calculated by partitioning the patients into deciles based on the predicted risk and in each group calculating the mean predicted risk and the fraction of the patients who experienced the outcome during the time at risk. We then plot these ten points (predicted risk on the y-axis and observed risk on the x-axis) and see whether they fall on the $x = y$ line, indicating the model is well calibrated. An example calibration plot is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Example of a calibration plot.

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We can fit a linear model using the points to calculate the intercept (which should be close to zero) and the gradient (which should be close to one). If the gradient is greater than one then the model is assigning a higher risk than the true risk and if the gradient is less than one the model is assigning a lower risk than the true risk. Note that we also implemented Smooth Calibration Curves in our R-package to better capture the non-linear relationship between predicted and observed risk.

2.4 Designing a Patient-Level Prediction Study

In this section we will briefly talk through the design choices that have to be made for a patient-level prediction study. In the patient-level prediction framework we enforce proper specification of the prediction problem by requiring the key choices to be explicitly defined.

2.4.1 Problem Definition

The first step is to clearly define the prediction problem itself. Interestingly, in many published papers the prediction problem is poorly defined, for example it is unclear how the index date (start of the target cohort) is defined. A poorly defined prediction problem does not allow for external validation by others, let alone implementation in clinical practice.

Here we use a “treatment safety” type prediction problem as an example:

Angioedema is a well-known side-effect of ACE inhibitors, and the incidence of angioedema reported in the labeling for ACE inhibitors is in the range of 0.1% to 0.7%. (Byrd et al., 2006) Monitoring patients for this adverse effect is important, because although angioedema is rare, it may be life-threatening, leading to respiratory arrest and death. (Norman et al., 2013) Further, if angioedema is not initially recognized, it may lead to extensive and expensive workups before it is identified as a cause. (Norman et al., 2013; Thompson and Frable, 1993) Other than the higher risk among African-American patients, there are no known pre-disposing factors for the development of ACE inhibitor related angioedema. (Byrd et al., 2006) Most reactions occur within the first week or month of initial therapy and often within hours of the initial dose. (Cicardi et al., 2004) However, some cases may occur years after therapy has begun. (O’Mara and O’Mara, 1996) No diagnostic test is available that specifically identifies those at risk. If we could identify those at risk, doctors could act, for example by discontinuing the ACE inhibitor in favor of another hypertension drug.

We will apply the patient-level prediction framework to observational healthcare data to address the following patient-level prediction question:

Among patients who have just started on an ACE inhibitor for the first time, who will experience angioedema in the following year?

2.4.2 Study Population Definition

The final study population in which we will develop our model is often a subset of the target cohort, because we may for example apply criteria that are dependent on the outcome, or we want to perform sensitivity analyses with sub-populations of the target cohort. For this we have to answer the following questions:

- *What is the minimum amount of observation time we require before the start of the target cohort?* This choice could depend on the available patient time in the training data, but also on the time we expect to be available in the data sources we want to apply the model on in the future. The longer the minimum observation time, the more baseline history time is available for each person to use for feature extraction,

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but the fewer patients will qualify for analysis. Moreover, there could be clinical reasons to choose a short or longer look-back period. For our example, we will use a 365-day prior history as look-back period (washout period).

- *Can patients enter the target cohort multiple times?* In the target cohort definition, a person may qualify for the cohort multiple times during different spans of time, for example if they had different episodes of a disease or separate periods of exposure to a medical product. The cohort definition does not necessarily apply a restriction to only let the patients enter once, but in the context of a particular patient-level prediction problem we may want to restrict the cohort to the first qualifying episode. In our example, a person can only enter the target cohort once since our criteria was based on first use of an ACE inhibitor.
- *Do we allow persons to enter the cohort if they experienced the outcome before?* Do we allow persons to enter the target cohort if they experienced the outcome before qualifying for the target cohort? Depending on the particular patient-level prediction problem, there may be a desire to predict incident first occurrence of an outcome, in which case patients who have previously experienced the outcome are not at risk for having a first occurrence and therefore should be excluded from the target cohort. In other circumstances, there may be a desire to predict prevalent episodes, whereby patients with prior outcomes can be included in the analysis and the prior outcome itself can be a predictor of future outcomes. For our prediction example, we will choose not to include those with prior angioedema.
- *How do we define the period in which we will predict our outcome relative to the target cohort start?* We have to make two decisions to answer this question. First, does the time-at-risk window start at the date of the start of the target cohort or later? Arguments to make it start later could be that we want to avoid outcomes that were entered late in the record that actually occurred before the start of the target cohort or we want to leave a gap where interventions to prevent the outcome could theoretically be implemented. Second, we need to define the time-at-risk by setting the risk window end, as some specification of days offset relative to the target cohort start or end dates. For our problem we will predict in a time-at-risk window starting 1 day after the start of the target cohort up to 365 days later.
- *Do we require a minimum amount of time-at-risk?* We have to decide if we want to include patients that did not experience the outcome but did leave the database earlier than the end of our time-at-risk period. These patients may experience the outcome when we no longer observe them. For our prediction problem we decide to answer this question with “yes,” requiring a minimum time-at-risk for that reason. Furthermore, we have to decide if this constraint also applies to persons who experienced the out- come or we will include all persons with the outcome irrespective of their total time at risk. For example, if the outcome is death, then persons with the outcome are likely censored before the full time-at-risk period is complete.

2.4.3 Model Development Settings

To develop the prediction model, we have to decide which algorithm(s) we like to train. We see the selection of the best algorithm for a certain prediction problem as an empirical question, i.e. we prefer to let the data speak for itself and try different approaches to find the best one. In our framework we have therefore implemented many algorithms, and allow others to be added. In this example, to keep things simple, we select just one algorithm: Gradient Boosting Machines.

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Furthermore, we have to decide on the covariates that we will use to train our model. In our example, we like to add gender, age, all conditions, drugs and drug groups, and visit counts. We will look for these clinical events in the year before and any time prior to the index date.

2.4.4 Model Evaluation

Finally, we have to define how we will evaluate our model. For simplicity, we here choose internal validation. We have to decide how we divide our dataset in a training and test dataset and how we assign patients to these two sets. Here we will use a typical 75% - 25% split. Note that for very large datasets we could use more data for training.

2.4.5 Study Summary

We have now completely defined our study as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Main design choices for our study

Choice	Description
Target cohort	Patients who have just started on an ACE inhibitor for the first time. Patients are excluded if they have less than 365 days of prior observation time or have prior angioedema.
Outcome cohort	Angioedema.
Time-at-risk	1 day until 365 days from cohort start. We will require at least 364 days at risk.
Model	Gradient Boosting Machine with hyper-parameters ntree: 5000, max depth: 4 or 7 or 10 and learning rate: 0.001 or 0.01 or 0.1 or 0.9. Covariates will include gender, age, conditions, drugs, drug groups, and visit count. Data split: 75% train - 25% test, randomly assigned by person.

2.5 Implementing the Study

To implement the study we have to generate the Target and Outcome cohort in a cohort table in the CDM, i.e., we have know for each patients if and when they enter these cohorts. This can be done using custom SQL code or it can be done in the ATLAS tool that has an interface that allows the user to build a cohort defintion and generate the cohorts.

To then extract all the candidate predictors and execute the model training and evaluation we have two options:

- 1) We create a script in R that runs all these steps following the guidance in the vignette ([link](#)) and section 13.7 “Implementing the study in R” of the Book of OHDSI
- 2) We use the recently added functionality in ATLAS to define the study and automatically generate an R package in the interface that can be run against the CDM without custom programming steps

Here we will briefly describe the second option using ATLAS.

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Atlas has in its left hand side menu a **Prediction** button that allows you to specify a new prediction problem.

In the Prediction design function, there are four sections: Prediction Problem Settings, Analysis Settings, Execution Settings, and Training Settings. Each of these sections is a form in which all the design choices can be set, see for example the Prediction Problems Settings section in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Prediction Problem settings.

Here you can select the Target and Outcome cohorts for which you want to run a study. It is very powerful to be able to specify multiple cohorts here, this allows you, for example, to automatically run prediction models for a number of definitions of the Target Cohort as a sensitivity analysis.

For details on these sections we refer to section 13.6 “Implementing the study in Atlas” of the Book of OHDSI.

Importing and Exporting a Study

To export a study, the user can click on the “Export” tab under “Utilities.” ATLAS will produce JSON that can be directly copied and pasted into a file that contains all of the data, such as the study name, cohort definitions, models selected, covariates, settings, needed to run the study.

To import a study, click on the “Import” tab under “Utilities.” Paste the contents of a patient-level prediction study JSON into this window, then click on the Import button below the other tab buttons. Note that this will overwrite all previous settings for that study, so this is typically done using a new, empty study design.

Downloading the Study Package

A very powerful feature is that the tool automatically generates an R package for you that will execute the full study. In the “Download Study Package” section under “Utilities”, the user can enter a descriptive name for the R package and download the Study Package.

2.6 Executing the Study

To execute the study, the user needs to build the study package in R (R Studio) and follow the instructions in the Readme file, i.e. fill in the connection details to the database etc.

The study package will then run all the specified prediction cohorts for all the settings specified in ATLAS and will create a results folder per prediction problem containing the final model and its performance measures.

2.7 Results Dissemination

We have added much functionality to view the study result, e.g. several plotting functions. Moreover, we added Shiny Applications (interactive dashboards) that allows the user to look in depth in the performance measures and final models.

Figure 6, show the Shiny App for a single study:

Figure 6. Summary evaluation statistics in Shiny App.

This app also hosts all the graphs, e.g. ROC plot.

Furthermore, we developed a second Shiny App that allows you to compare models as show in Figure 7.

The screenshot shows a Shiny application interface with a table of model performance metrics. The table has columns for Analysis ID, Dev, Val, T, O, Model, TAR start, TAR end, AUC, AUPRC, T Size, O Count, and O Incidence (%). Four models are listed, each with its respective performance values.

Analysis	Dev	Val	T	O	Model	TAR start	TAR end	AUC	AUPRC	T Size	O Count	O Incidence (%)
Analysis_1	Optum claims	Optum claims	New users of ACE inhibitors as first-line monotherapy for hypertension	Acute myocardial infarction events	Lasso Logistic Regression	1	365	0.74486	0.03094	87757	650	0.74068
Analysis_3	Optum claims	Optum claims	New users of ACE inhibitors as first-line monotherapy for hypertension	Angioedema events	Lasso Logistic Regression	1	365	0.60323	0.00254	87615	148	0.16892
Analysis_5	Optum claims	Optum claims	New users of ACE inhibitors as first-line monotherapy for hypertension	Acute myocardial infarction events	Random forest	1	365	0.71667	0.03102	87757	650	0.74068
Analysis_7	Optum claims	Optum claims	New users of ACE inhibitors as first-line monotherapy for hypertension	Angioedema events	Random forest	1	365	0.64163	0.02447	87615	148	0.16892

Figure 7. The Shiny summary page containing performance metrics for each trained model.

This tool is pretty advanced already, e.g., it allows the use to select the prediction threshold of a model as shown in Figure 8 and has interactive plots to visualize the prevalence of the predictors in those with and without the outcome as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 8. The summary performance measures at a set threshold.

Figure 9. Model summary plots. Each dot corresponds to a variable included in the model.

2.8 Additional functionality

The package can generate a **Validation Study R package** that can be sent to other databases to externally validate the model. This is a very important step for model acceptance which would have been very difficult to implement without the OMOP CDM and the developed analytical pipeline.

Furthermore, we add a feature in the package that can automatically generate a **journal paper** following the TRIPOD guidelines (2). It contains place holders for all sections with predefined text, including a fully populated methods section based on the specifications and a results section containing all the artefacts such as an attrition diagram and the performance plots. If an external validation has been performed these results will be added as well. Optionally, a “Table 1” can be added that contains data on covariates for the target population.

There are a lot of additional features being added or evaluated that we will discuss in more detail in upcoming deliverables, for example Learning Curves, Ensemble training etc.

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3. POPULATION-LEVEL EFFECT ESTIMATION

For a full explanation of the Population-Level Effect Estimation pipeline we refer to the Book-Of-OHDSI Chapter 12 “Population-Level Effect Estimation” led by Martijn Schuemie (JANSSEN), Patrick Ryan (JANSSEN), and OHDSI collaborators David Madigan (Columbia University) and Marc Suchard (UCLA). , and the CohortMethod R-Package page that contains more advanced functionality not covered in the book: <https://ohdsi.github.io/CohortMethod/>

Observational healthcare data, such as administrative claims and electronic health records, offer opportunities to generate real-world evidence about the effect of treatments that can meaningfully improve the lives of patients. In this chapter we focus on population-level effect estimation, which refers to the estimation of average causal effects of exposures (e.g. medical interventions such as drug exposures or procedures) on specific health outcomes of interest. In what follows, we consider two different estimation tasks:

- **Direct effect estimation:** estimating the effect of an exposure on the risk of an outcome, as compared to no exposure.
- **Comparative effect estimation:** estimating the effect of an exposure (the target exposure) on the risk of an outcome, as compared to another exposure (the comparator exposure).

In both cases, the patient-level causal effect contrasts a factual outcome, i.e., what happened to the exposed patient, with a counterfactual outcome, i.e., what would have happened had the exposure not occurred (direct) or had a different exposure occurred (comparative). Since any one patient reveals only the factual outcome (the fundamental problem of causal inference), the various effect estimation designs employ different analytic devices to shed light on the counterfactual outcomes.

Use-cases for population-level effect estimation include treatment selection, safety surveillance, and comparative effectiveness. Methods can test specific hypotheses one at a time (e.g. ‘signal evaluation’) or explore multiple-hypotheses-at-once (e.g. ‘signal detection’). In all cases, the objective remains the same: to produce a high-quality estimate of the causal effect.

In this section we first describe the Cohort Methods Design, one of various population-level estimation study designs all of which are implemented as R packages in the [OHDSI Methods Library](#). We then detail the design of an example estimation study, followed by step-by-step guides of how to implement the design. Finally, we review the various outputs generated by the study, including study diagnostics and effect size estimates.

3.1 Cohort Method Design

The cohort method attempts to emulate a randomized clinical trial. ([Hernan and Robins, 2016](#)) Subjects that are observed to initiate one treatment (the target) are compared to subjects initiating another treatment (the comparator) and are followed for a specific amount of time following treatment initiation, for example the time they stay on the treatment. We can specify the questions we wish to answer in a cohort study by making the five choices highlighted in Table 3.

Table 3: Main design choices in a comparative cohort design.

Choice	Description
Target cohort	A cohort representing the target treatment
Comparator cohort	A cohort representing the comparator treatment
Outcome cohort	A cohort representing the outcome of interest
Time-at-risk	At what time (often relative to the target and comparator cohort start and end dates) do we consider the risk of the outcome?
Model	The model used to estimate the effect while adjusting for differences between the target and comparator

The choice of model specifies, among others, the type of outcome model. For example, we could use a logistic regression, which evaluates whether or not the outcome has occurred, and produces an odds ratio. A logistic regression assumes the time-at-risk is of the same length for both target and comparator, or is irrelevant. Alternatively, we could choose a Poisson regression which estimates the incidence rate ratio, assuming a constant incidence rate. Often a Cox regression is used which considers time to first outcome to estimate the hazard ratio, assuming proportional hazards between target and comparator.

Figure 10. *The new-user cohort design. Subjects observed to initiate the target treatment are compared to those initiating the comparator treatment. To adjust for differences between the two treatment groups several adjustment strategies can be used, such as stratification, matching, or weighting by the propensity score, or by adding baseline characteristics to the outcome model. The characteristics included in the propensity model or outcome model are captured prior to treatment initiation.*

A key concern is that the patients receiving the target treatment may systematically differ from those receiving the comparator treatment. For example, suppose the target cohort is on average 60 years old, whereas the comparator cohort is on average 40 years old. Comparing target to comparator with respect to any age-related health outcome (e.g. stroke) might then show substantial differences between the cohorts. An uninformed investigator might reach the conclusion there is a causal association between the target treatment and stroke as compared to the comparator. More prosaically or commonplace, the investigator might conclude that there exist target patients that experienced stroke that would not have done so had they received the comparator. This conclusion could well be entirely incorrect! Maybe those target patients disproportionately experienced stroke simply because they are older; maybe the target patients that experienced stroke might well have done so even if they had received the comparator. In this context, age is a “confounder.” One mechanism to deal with confounders in observational studies is through propensity scores.

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3.1.1 Propensity Scores

In a randomized trial, a (virtual) coin toss assigns patients to their respective groups. Thus, by design, the probability that a patient receives the target treatment as against the comparator treatment does not relate in any way to patient characteristics such as age. The coin has no knowledge of the patient, and, what's more, we know with certainty the exact probability that a patient receives the target exposure. As a consequence, and with increasing confidence as the number of patients in the trial increases, the two groups of patients essentially *cannot* differ systematically with respect to *any* patient characteristic. This guaranteed balance holds true for characteristics that the trial measured (such as age) as well as characteristics that the trial failed to measure, such as patient genetic factors.

For a given patient, the *propensity score* (PS) is the probability that that patient received the target treatment as against the comparator (3). In a balanced two-arm randomized trial, the propensity score is 0.5 for every patient. In a propensity score- adjusted observational study, we estimate the probability of a patient receiving the target treatment based on what we can observe in the data on and before the time of treatment initiation (irrespective of the treatment they actually received). This is a straightforward predictive modeling application; we fit a model (e.g. a logistic regression) that predicts whether a subject receives the target treatment, and use this model to generate predicted probabilities (the PS) for each subject. Unlike in a standard randomized trial, different patients will have different probabilities of receiving the target treatment. The PS can be used in several ways including matching target subjects to comparator subjects with similar PS, stratifying the study population based on the PS, or weighting subjects using Inverse Probability of Treatment Weighting (IPTW) derived from the PS. When matching we can select just one comparator subject for each target subject, or we can allow more than one comparator subject per target subject, a technique known as variable-ratio matching (4).

For example, suppose we use one-on-one PS matching, and that Jan has an *a priori* probability of 0.4 of receiving the target treatment and in fact receives the target treatment. If we can find a patient (named Jun) that also had an *a priori* probability of 0.4 of receiving the target treatment but in fact received the comparator, the comparison of Jan and Jun's outcomes is like a mini-randomized trial, at least with respect to measured confounders. This comparison will yield an estimate of the Jan-Jun causal contrast that is as good as the one randomization would have produced. Estimation then proceeds as follows: for every patient that received the target, find one or more matched patients that received the comparator but had the same prior probability of receiving the target. Compare the outcome for the target patient with the outcomes for the comparator patients within each of these matched groups.

Propensity scoring controls for measured confounders. In fact, if treatment assignment is "strongly ignorable" given measured characteristics, propensity scoring will yield an unbiased estimate of the causal effect. "Strongly ignorable" essentially means that there are no unmeasured confounders, and that the measured confounders are adjusted for appropriately. Unfortunately, this is not a testable assumption. See Chapter 18 in the Book of OHDSI for further discussion of this issue.

3.1.2 Variable Selection

In the past, PS were computed based on manually selected characteristics, and although the OHDSI tools can support such practices, we prefer using many generic characteristics (i.e. characteristics that are not selected based on the specific exposures and outcomes in the study) (5). These characteristics include demographics, as well as all diagnoses, drug exposures, measurement, and medical procedures observed prior to and on the day of treatment initiation. A model typically involves 10,000 to 100,000 unique characteristics, which we fit using large-scale regularized regression (6) implemented in the [Cyclops](#) package.

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In essence, we let the data decide which characteristics are predictive of the treatment assignment and should be included in the model.

Some have argued that a data-driven approach to covariate selection that does not depend on clinical expertise to specify the “right” causal structure runs the risk of erroneously including so-called instrumental variables and colliders, thus increasing variance and potentially introducing bias. (7) However, these concerns are unlikely to have a large impact in real-world scenarios. (8) Furthermore, in medicine the true causal structure is rarely known, and when different researchers are asked to identify the ‘right’ covariates to include for a specific research question, each researcher invariably comes up with a different list, thus making the process irreproducible. Most importantly, our diagnostics such as inspection of the propensity model, evaluating balance on all covariates, and including negative controls would identify most problems related to colliders and instrumental variables.

3.1.3 Caliper

Since propensity scores fall on a continuum from 0 to 1, exact matching is rarely possible. Instead, the matching process finds patients that match the propensity score of a target patient(s) within some tolerance known as a “caliper.” Following (9), we use a default caliper of 0.2 standard deviations on the logit scale.

3.1.4 Overlap: Preference Score

The propensity method requires that matching patients exist! As such, a key diagnostic shows the distribution of the propensity scores in the two groups. To facilitate interpretation, the OHDSI tools plot a transformation of the propensity score called the “preference score” (10). The preference score adjusts for the “market share” of the two treatments. For example, if 10% of patients receive the target treatment (and 90% receive the comparator treatment), then patients with a preference score of 0.5 have a 10% probability of receiving the target treatment. Mathematically, the preference score is

Good practice always checks that the PS adjustment succeeds in creating balanced groups of patients. For each patient characteristic, this plots the standardized difference between means between the two exposure groups before and after PS adjustment. Some guidelines recommend an after-adjustment standardized difference upper bound of 0.1 (11).

$$\ln\left(\frac{F}{1-F}\right) = \ln\left(\frac{S}{1-S}\right) - \ln\left(\frac{P}{1-P}\right)$$

Where F is the preference score, S is the propensity score, and P is the proportion of patients receiving the target treatment.

Walker et al. (10) discuss the concept of “empirical equipoise.” They accept exposure pairs as emerging from empirical equipoise if at least half of the exposures are to patients with a preference score of between 0.3 and 0.7.

3.2 Designing a PLE Study

3.2.1 Problem Definition

ACE inhibitors (ACEi) are widely used in patients with hypertension or ischemic heart disease, especially those with other comorbidities such as congestive heart failure, diabetes mellitus, or chronic kidney disease (12). Angioedema, a serious and sometimes life-threatening adverse event that usually manifests as swelling

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of the lips, tongue, mouth, larynx, pharynx, or periorbital region, has been linked to the use of these medications (13). However, limited information is available about the absolute and relative risks for angioedema associated with the use of these medications. Existing evidence is primarily based on investigations of specific cohorts (e.g., predominantly male veterans or Medicaid beneficiaries) whose findings may not be generalizable to other populations, or based on investigations with few events, which provide unstable risk estimates (14). Several observational studies compare ACEi to beta-blockers for the risk of angioedema, (15) but beta-blockers are no longer recommended as first-line treatment of hypertension (16). A viable alternative treatment could be thiazides or thiazide-like diuretics (THZ), which could be just as effective in managing hypertension and its associated risks such as acute myocardial infarction (AMI), but without increasing the risk of angioedema.

We can now use the population-level estimation framework to observational healthcare data to address the following comparative estimation questions:

1. What is the risk of angioedema in new users of ACE inhibitors compared to new users of thiazide and thiazide-like diuretics?
2. What is the risk of acute myocardial infarction in new users of ACE inhibitors compared to new users of thiazide and thiazide-like diuretics?

3.2.2 Target and Comparator

We consider patients new users if their first observed treatment for hypertension was monotherapy with any active ingredient in either the ACEi or THZ class. We define mono therapy as not starting on any other anti-hypertensive drug in the seven days following treatment initiation. We require patients to have at least one year of prior continuous observation in the database before first exposure and a recorded hypertension diagnosis at or in the year preceding treatment initiation.

3.2.3 Outcome

We define angioedema as any occurrence of an angioedema condition concept during an inpatient or emergency room (ER) visit, and require there to be no angioedema diagnosis recorded in the seven days prior. We define AMI as any occurrence of an AMI condition concept during an inpatient or ER visit, and require there to be no AMI diagnosis record in the 180 days prior.

3.2.4 Time-At-Risk

We define time-at-risk to start on the day after treatment initiation, and stop when exposure stops, allowing for a 30-day gap between subsequent drug exposures.

3.2.5 Model

We fit a PS model using the default set of covariates, including demographics, conditions, drugs, procedures, measurements, observations, and several co-morbidity scores. We exclude ACEi and THZ from the covariates. We perform variable-ratio matching and condition the Cox regression on the matched sets.

3.2.6 Study Summary

Table 4 shows the summary of all the design choices we made for our comparative cohort study.

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Table 4: Main design choices for our comparative cohort study.

Choice	Value
Target cohort	New users of ACE inhibitors as first-line monotherapy for hypertension.
Comparator cohort	New users of thiazides or thiazide-like diuretics as first-line monotherapy for hypertension.
Outcome cohort	Angioedema or acute myocardial infarction.
Time-at-risk	Starting the day after treatment initiation, stopping when exposure stops.
Model	Cox proportional hazards model using variable-ratio matching.

3.3 Implementing a PLE Study

To implement the study we can either follow the Vignette of the CohortMethod R Package or use ATLAS to define our study. Once we have fully defined our study, we can export it as an executable R package. This package contains everything that is needed to execute the study at a site that has data in CDM. This includes the cohort definitions that can be used to instantiate the target, comparator and outcome cohorts, the negative control concept set and logic to create the negative control outcome cohorts, as well as the R code to execute the analysis.

For more details on the implementation and execution of the Population-Level Effect Estimation study we refer to sections [12.7](#) “Implementing the study using ATLAS” and [12.8](#) “Implementing the study using R” in The Book of OHDSI.

3.4 Study Outputs

The estimates are only valid if several assumptions have been met. We use a wide set of diagnostics to evaluate whether this is the case. These are available in the results produced by the R package generated by ATLAS, or can be generated on the fly using specific R functions.

For example, we first need to evaluate whether the target and comparator cohort are to some extent comparable. For this we can compute the Area Under the Receiver Operator Curve (AUC) statistic for the propensity model. An AUC of 1 indicates the treatment assignment was completely predictable based on baseline covariates, and that the two groups are therefore incomparable. We can use the computePsAucfunction to compute the AUC, which in our example is 0.79. Using the plotPs function, we can also generate the preference score distribution as shown in Figure 11. Here we see that for many people the treatment they received was predictable, but there is also a large amount of overlap, indicating that adjustment can be used to select comparable groups.

Figure 11. Preference score distribution.

In section [12.9](#) “Study Outputs” in The Book of OHDSI other important diagnostics are discussed like the Covariate Balance, Follow Up and Power, Kaplan-Meier, and the Effect Size Estimate.

OHDSI has also created Shiny Applications to disseminate study results as for example for the Large-Scale Evidence Generation and Evaluation across a Network of Databases (LEGEND) project that studied the Comprehensive comparative effectiveness and safety of first-line antihypertensive drug classes (17) : <https://data.ohdsi.org/LegendBasicViewer/>

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4. RISK STRATIFIED EFFECT ESTIMATION

Generalizability of study results and applicability to a specific patient move in opposite directions. When patients differ from one another in many key determinants of the outcome of interest –and consequently in the potential benefits and harms of therapy– it can be unclear to whom the overall average benefit-harm trade-offs actually apply. Precision medicine aims to tailor treatment to individual patients. As such, analysis of heterogeneity of treatment effect (HTE), i.e. non-random variation in the direction or magnitude of a treatment effect for individuals within a population, is the cornerstone of precision medicine; its goal is to predict the optimal treatments at the individual level, accounting for an individual’s risk for harm and benefit outcomes.

In this section we describe the application of a risk modeling predictive approach to the assessment of treatment effect heterogeneity (HTE) using the first version of the RiskStratifiedEstimation R package we developed in WP3.

The method involves 4 main steps (see also Figure 12):

- **Definition of the problem:** For this step we need to define (at least) 3 essential cohorts: (1) the treatment cohort, containing the set of patients receiving the treatment of interest; (2) the comparator cohort, containing the set of patients receiving the comparator treatment; (3) the outcome cohort(s), containing the set of patients having the outcome(s) of interest.
- **Identification of the database:** We need to select the database(s) on which we will assess treatment effect heterogeneity. We need to make sure that the cohorts contain enough patients to be able to perform the risk stratification.
- **Prediction step:** Combine the treatment and comparator cohorts into a single cohort for prediction and then provide the settings required for prediction based on the PatientLevelPrediction package. This means that we need to define the time-at-risk (time interval within which we want to predict), the set of predictive covariates and the prediction algorithm to be used (along with its settings).
- **Estimation step:** Divide the treatment population in a pre-specified number of equal-sized strata based on baseline risk and estimate the absolute and relative treatment effects.

Figure 12: Risk Stratified Estimation method explanation

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4.1 Designing a RSE Study

To explain the method, we consider some of the treatments and outcomes assessed in the Large-scale Evidence Generation in Network of Databases (LEGEND) study for hypertension (17). The treatment cohort contains patients with a hypertension diagnosis within the database that receive angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitors, followed from the time of initiation until the time of cessation. The comparator cohort contains the set of patients within the database with a hypertension diagnosis that receive beta blockers. We also consider 2 outcome cohorts. The first contains all patients found in the database that have at least one occurrence of cardiovascular disease (CVD). The second contains all patients with an occurrence of cough. We consider CVD as the main outcome of interest that we are trying to prevent in the study and cough as a common side-effect of ACE-inhibitors. Cohort definitions are available online [here](#).

After defining the problem, we need to select the database on which we will assess treatment effect heterogeneity. We need to make sure that the defined cohorts are of adequate size to perform the analysis. This is relevant to all cohorts defined. Very small treatment or comparator cohorts reduce the power of our analyses restricting the minimum detectable differences. Due to the stratified approach of the framework this aspect is very relevant. The size of the outcome cohorts is very important for both the prediction and the estimation steps. In the former case, low events per variable may limit the prediction performance, while in the latter case, risk stratification may result in very few or even no observed cases in the lower strata.

4.2 Implementing a RSE Study

4.2.1 Cohort instantiation

The Cohorts need to be created using ATLAS or through custom SQL code. This process is described in detail in the earlier sections and also in The Book of OHDSI in [Chapter 10](#) “Defining Cohorts”.

4.2.2 Study script creation

After the cohorts have been created and have been extracted on a specific database, we can proceed with the creation of the script that will perform the defined study. For this part 7 types of input need to be created:

connection details

The connection details contain the type of database, server, username, password etc as described in detail in the [DatabaseConnector R Package](#).

```
connectionDetails <- DatabaseConnector::createConnectionDetails (dbms = dbms,
                                                                server = server,
                                                                user = "joe",
                                                                password =
                                                                "secret", port =
                                                                port)
```

analysis settings

The analysis settings refer to information that define the structure of the study and can be used to identify it. The analysis id is a unique identifier of the present study. The treatment cohort id refers to the unique identifier of the treatment cohort definition. In our case, that is 1001 and refers to the extracted hypertensive patients receiving ACE-inhibitors. The comparator cohort id refers to the unique identifier of the comparator

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cohort. In our case this is 1002 and refers to the extracted cohort of hypertensive patients receiving beta blockers; the outcome ids that refer to the unique identifiers of the outcome cohorts. A very important characteristic of the analysis settings is the analysis matrix, that dictates which comparisons are to be made. The columns of this square boolean matrix refer to risk stratification outcomes and the rows to estimation outcomes. Therefore, the default diagonal matrix defines the following analyses:

- 1 Within strata of CVD risk estimate relative and absolute treatment effects of CVD events.
- 2 Within strata of cough risk estimate relative and absolute treatment effects of coughing events.

We can create the analysis settings using the following code:

```
analysisSettings <- createAnalysisSettings (analysisId = "vignette_demonstration",
                                           treatmentCohortId = 1001,
                                           comparatorCohortId = 1002,
                                           outcomeIds = c(134, 153),
                                           analysisMatrix = diag(2)),
                                           verbosity = "INFO",
                                           saveDirectory =
                                           "path/to/save/directory")
```

Database settings

The database settings contain relevant information on the database we want to access. These include the database schema and the tables where the cohorts of interest are stored. Note that we also need to create a table containing the merged treatment and comparator cohorts that will be used to derive the prediction models (requires write permission). Database settings can be created from:

```
databaseSettings <- createDatabaseSettings (cdmDatabaseSchema = "cdm_truven_mdcd_v780.dbo",
                                           cohortDatabaseSchema =
                                           "Scratch.dbo",
                                           outcomeDatabaseSchema =
                                           "Scratch.dbo",
                                           resultsDatabaseSchema =
                                           "Scratch.dbo",
                                           exposureDatabaseSchema =
                                           "Scratch.dbo", cohortTable =
                                           "ace_beta_cohorts", outcomeTable =
                                           "ace_beta_outcomes", exposureTable
                                           = "ace_beta_cohorts",
                                           mergedCohortTable =
                                           "ace_beta_merged",
                                           attributeDefinitionTable =
                                           "ace_beta_def", cohortAttributeTable
                                           = "ace_beta_attr")
```

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Extracting the data

There are two data objects that need to be defined. The prediction data object that will be used for the derivation of the prediction models used to risk stratify patients and the estimation data object that will be used to estimate propensity scores and estimate treatment effects within risk strata.

```
getDataSettings <- createGetDataSettings (getPlpDataSettings =
  createGetPlpDataArgs (washoutPeriod = 365), getCmDataSettings =
  createGetCmDataArgs (washoutPeriod = 365))
```

Covariate settings

```
covariateSettings <-
  createGetCovariateSettings (covariateSettingsCm =
    FeatureExtraction::createCovariateSettings (
      useDemographicsGender = TRUE,
      useDemographicsAge = TRUE,
      useConditionOccurrenceLongTerm = TRUE,
      useConditionOccurrenceShortTerm = TRUE,
      useDrugExposureLongTerm = TRUE,
      useDrugExposureShortTerm = TRUE,
      useDrugEraLongTerm = TRUE,
      useDrugEraShortTerm = TRUE,
      useCharlsonIndex = TRUE,
      addDescendantsToExclude = TRUE,
      excludedCovariateConceptIds =
        excludedCovariateConceptIds,
      addDescendantsToInclude =
        TRUE),
    covariateSettingsPlp =
      FeatureExtraction::createCovariateSettings (
        useDemographicsGender = TRUE,
        useDemographicsAge = TRUE,
        useConditionOccurrenceLongTerm =
          TRUE,
        useConditionOccurrenceShortTerm =
          TRUE, useDrugExposureLongTerm =
          TRUE, useDrugExposureShortTerm
          = TRUE, useDrugEraLongTerm =
          TRUE, useDrugEraShortTerm =
          TRUE, useCharlsonIndex = TRUE,
        addDescendantsToExclude =
          TRUE))
```

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The purpose of the covariate settings is twofold. In the prediction step they define the set of candidate predictors for the development of the model. In the estimation step they define the set of candidate confounders to be considered for the estimation of the propensity scores. In both cases we use the same covariate settings using a large set of standardized covariates:

Population settings

The population settings contain additional restrictions for the definitive target populations. Again, in this case we need to define the target population in the prediction step, based on which we will develop the prediction models. In the estimation step the population settings will define the population from which the propensity score models will be derived, and the treatment effects will be estimated. The final populations may contain slightly different patients. We can define the population by:

```
populationSettings <-
  createPopulationSettings (populationPlpSettings =
    createPopulationPlpSettingsArgs (riskWindowEnd = 365,
      minTimeAtRisk = 364), populationCmSettings =
    createPopulationCmSettingsArgs (
      removeDuplicateSubjects = "keep first",
      removeSubjectsWithPriorOutcome = TRUE,
      riskWindowStart = 1, riskWindowEnd = 9999,
      addExposureDaysToEnd = FALSE, minDaysAtRisk =
      1))
```

Run settings

Finally, we need to define the settings based on which the algorithms in the prediction and estimation steps will be run. For example, in the prediction step we need to define the prediction algorithm to be used along with the hyperparameter parameter search strategy.

```
runSettings <-
  createRunSettings (runPlpSettings =
    createRunPlpSettingsArgs (), runCmSettings =
    createRunCmSettingsArgs (
      psMethod = "inversePtWeighted", effectEstimationSettings =
      createCreatePWArgs (), psSettings = createCreatePsArgs (),
      fitOutcomeModelsThreads = 2, timePoint = 365
    )
  )
```

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In the estimation step the settings we need to define are the propensity score method to be used for the estimation of the effects within risk strata and the time point at which we will assess absolute and relative risk differences. Since we mostly deal with time-to-event data this means that absolute risk reduction is estimated based on the difference on the Kaplan-Meier estimates at the specific time point. The run settings can be created from:

4.4 Study Outputs

The RiskStratifiedEstimation package allows for the construction of several plots. We have already mentioned that we can obtain the default plots provided from the PatientLevelPrediction package for model evaluation. Additionally, we can derive the propensity score diagnostics described in the CohortMethod package vignette.

4.4.1 Balance diagnostics

Using the code presented below we can plot the covariate balance in the weighted population of the 4th (highest) risk stratum.


```
plotCovariateBalance(ps = result$ps[[4]],
                    cohortMethodData =
                    cohortMethodData,
                    calculateWeights = FALSE,
                    showNotBalancedCovariateIds =
                    TRUE)
```

4.4.3 Weighted Kaplan-Meier

Using the code presented below we can produce plots of the weighted Kaplan-Meier estimates within risk strata. The time interval of interest is one year (365 days). Again, we consider the case of the 4th risk stratum.

```
plotWeightedKM(dataKM = result$dataKM[[4]],
               xlim = c(0,
                       365), ylim =
               c(.7, 1), ci =
               FALSE)
```


4.4.4 Analysis result

Finally, we can produce an analysis summary plot using the code below. This plot contains the outcome rates in the propensity weighted populations along with the absolute and relative (hazard ratios) risk differences.

```

comparisonPlot(dataARR = result$absoluteRiskReduction,
               dataRRR = result$relativeRiskReduction,
               cases = result$cases,
               ylimRRR = c(.4, 1.1),
               ylimARR = c(-.01, .05),
               ylimCases = c(0, .125))
  
```

We can use such a plot to provide insight to the presence of HTE and draw useful conclusions on treatment assignment.

4.4 Study Example

As discussed above, the Large-scale Evidence Generation and Evaluation in a Network of Databases (LEGEND) study compared classes of hypertension drugs for their relative treatment effect on multiple outcomes (17). The absolute treatment effect (absolute risk reduction) of one drug class versus another often depends on baseline outcome risk. We performed a risk-based re-analysis of the LEGEND study, comparing the absolute risk difference of angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitors versus beta blockers for multiple outcomes. The analyses we performed with regard to baseline 2-year risk of total cardiovascular disease (CVD) risk.

For our analyses we considered the following databases: - IBM MarketScan® Multi-State Medicaid Database(MDCD) - IBM MarketScan® Medicare Supplemental Database (MDCR) - IBM MarketScan® Commercial Database (CCEA)

We predicted personalized CVD risk using LASSO logistic regression on the combined ACE-inhibitor and beta blocker cohorts. We estimated propensity scores using LASSO logistic regression within quartiles of predicted CVD risk. For balancing covariates within CVD risk quartiles we used inverse probability of treatment weighting. Finally, we estimated absolute risk reduction for each LEGEND outcome from the difference of the weighted treatment-specific (ACE-inhibitors vs beta blockers) Kaplan-Meier estimators within quartiles of predicted CVD risk. The overall results of the study in providing all results in the highest and lowest CVD risk quartiles can be found in Figure 14 on the next page.

Finally, more thorough inspection of the results can be done in the shiny application we developed which is shown below and made available online [here](#).

Figure 13. The Heterogeneity of Treatment Effect Shiny Application.

Figure 14. Study results in the highest and lowest CVD risk quartiles on three databases ([Link](#))

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5. NEXT STEPS

In the first year, major steps have been taken in the analytical pipeline for personalized medicine. The EHDEN contributions included mainly improvements in the Patient-Level Prediction Framework and the Risk Stratified Estimation pipeline. This would not have been possible without the close collaboration with the OHDSI community.

It is important to mention that these pipelines have already been used for study-a-thons in EHDEN, i.e. focused meeting where a group of researchers, clinicians, and data custodian meet for a week and design, implement, and execute a study to answer a clinically important question. A good example is the recently published study in Lancet Rheumatology describing the effectiveness and safety associated with unicompartmental versus total knee replacement that used the Population-Level Effect Estimation pipeline (online first: [link](#)). The same study-at-thon resulted in a publication in the Patient-Level Prediction field that is currently under review (see also Annex 1, Poster 1). In the upcoming period many more study-a-thons will be organized, starting with a study-a-thon in Barcelona in January 2020 focused on Inflammatory Arthritis.

5.1 Additional Methodological Research

In the 1st year of EHDEN we have also started additional methodological research on the following topics:

- 1 Learning curves research to better understand the need of big data for prediction model development. This has resulted in a poster at the European OHDSI Symposium (see Poster 4 in Annex 1). We are currently running a large-scale study to better understand how much data we need for patient-level prediction
- 2 We compared multiple strategies for ensemble training and are currently preparing a publication on this topic. This will result in further extensions of the PLP R Package.
- 3 The use of unstructured data in prediction is being explored and will be an important focus in the upcoming period. We will assess the additive value of this type of data and will compare multiple approaches to unlock its potential.
- 4 Deep Learning functionality has been added to the PLP package recently and we have started to assess its value on electronic health records.

Many more methodological research topics in the personalized medicine domain will be added in the upcoming year, e.g. the assessment of Machine Learning methods for propensity scores as alternative to LASSO, Explainable AI, Federated Learning etc.

5.2 Clinical Studies

In the next period we will continue to apply the developed analytical pipelines to clinically important use cases in close collaboration with WP1 and WP2.

An example is research we recently started in the osteoporosis field in reaction to the publication of the first-ever h2h trial in osteoporosis demonstrating the superiority of teriparatide vs risedronate (18), new guidelines now recommend the use of teriparatide in subjects at very high risk of fracture based on the FRAX prediction tool (19). Although this approach is of course better than the previous (just treat everyone at high risk with whatever you feel will work best), there are at least two issues that require attention:

- 1) there has been only one such trial;
- 2) the lack of evidence of treatment heterogeneity from previous trial data.

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The target cohort should contain women above the age of 50 initiating subcutaneous teriparatide. The comparator cohort should contain women above the age of 50 initiating oral bisphosphonate treatment. Patients with previous use of any anti-osteoporosis treatment in the past two years should be excluded from both cohorts along with patients with history of breast cancer or Paget’s disease. Finally, several effectiveness and safety outcomes should be considered. The former are fracture cases, containing spine/vertebral fractures, hip fractures or major osteoporotic fracture, a composite outcome including the previous 2 and also wrist/forearm and shoulder/proximal humerus fractures. The latter can be esophageal reactions, hypercalcemia, urolithiasis, orthostatic hypotension and others.

In the upcoming period we will apply the Risk Stratified Estimation Pipeline in this important clinical domain and will use this to drive the development of the R Package and dissemination tools.

5.3 Additional Tool Development

Finally, we will work on the development of a repository to store the resulting prediction models together with their development and external validation code. This will enable others to apply and validate the models on their CDM. Furthermore, we will incorporate the precision medicines pipeline into the Arachne tool to allow for semi-automatic execution in the EHDEN Data Network.

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ANNEXES

Annex 1 Research Posters

Poster 1 [\(Link\)](#)

	DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF PATIENT-LEVEL PREDICTION MODELS FOR ADVERSE OUTCOMES			
	FOLLOWING TOTAL KNEE ARTHROPLASTY ROSS D. WILLIAMS MSc (1), JENNA M. REPS PHD(2), PETER R. RIJNBEEK (1), DANI PRIETO ALHAMBRA PHD(3), PATRICK B. RYAN PHD(2) <small>(1) Erasmus University Medical Centre, Rotterdam; (2) Janssen Research and Development, Raritan, NJ, USA; (3) NDORMS, University of Oxford, Oxford, UK</small>			

INTRODUCTION

Elective total knee replacement (TKR) is a safe and cost-effective treatment for severe knee osteoarthritis (OA). Although complications following surgery are rare, prediction tools could help identify at risk subjects to target with preventative interventions.

Several guidelines provide stratification guidance based on a personalised risk profile. As such, a well validated clinical prediction model could have immediate impact on patient outcomes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

We conducted a multinational, multi-database cohort analysis using electronic health records and claims data from the US and the UK. In total we used 7 data sources mapped to the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership common data model (OMOP-CDM) and processed using the same analytical platform developed by the Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics (OHDSI) initiative. All subjects undergoing a first TKR, aged 40 years or older and registered in any of the contributing data sources for at least 1 year before surgery were included. Key adverse outcomes included post-operative (90-day) mortality, venous thrombo-embolism, infection, readmission; and long-term (5-year) revision surgery. Lasso logistic regression models were fit independently in 5 data sources and were then evaluated using discrimination and calibration. Those considered to have the potential for clinical use were then externally validated in other available datasets.

RESULTS

A total of 503,923 participants were included, with size per data source ranging from 158,549 to 15,292. Overall, 90-day mortality, VTE, infection and readmission were seen in a range 0.20%-0.32%, 1.7%-3.0%, 7.1%-9.0%, 2.2%-4.8% respectively. Five-year revision surgery was observed in 1.5%-3.1% of participants. None of the models for VTE or infection had good performance.

We trained models for 90-day mortality, VTE, infection, readmission, and 5-year revision. Only 90-day mortality yielded AUROC > 0.70, other outcomes were not predictive. 90-day mortality had AUC of 0.78 and 0.68 in internal validation on Optum and THIN respectively, and the Optum model got 0.69, 0.86, 0.76, 0.72 AUC in external validation on THIN, Columbia, Stanford and MDCD.

Figure 1. showing the calibration of the 90-day mortality Optum model

Development database	Validation database	AUROC	Test population	Outcome count in test population (% incidence)
OPTUM	OPTUM	0.78	38,166	88 (0.23)
OPTUM	THIN	0.69	40,950	81 (0.20)
OPTUM	CUMC	0.86	1853	6 (0.32)
OPTUM	STRIDE	0.76	2306	7 (0.30)
OPTUM	MDCD	0.72	15292	44 (0.29)
THIN	THIN	0.68	10,237	20 (0.20)
THIN	OPTUM	0.68	152,665	353 (0.23)
THIN	CUMC	0.84	1853	6 (0.32)
THIN	STRIDE	0.70	2306	7 (0.30)

Table 1. showing the internal and external AUROC of the two 90-day mortality models

CONCLUSION

We developed and externally validated prediction tools for the identification of subjects at high risk of short-term mortality as well as developing models for readmission, venous thromboembolism and long-term revision. The primary finding of the research is high predictability of short-term mortality and the unpredictability of the other investigated outcomes. This suggests that decisions can be stratified based on personalised risk of short-term mortality, however we were unable to produce adequate models for the other adverse outcomes.

Acknowledgements

Special thanks go to all attendees of the OHDSI_EHDEN Study-athon hosted by Ndorms in Oxford, UK who contributed

Poster 2 ([Link](#))

Dementia Prediction Using Routinely Collected Health Data

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Background

Dementia is a general term to describe various brain diseases (e.g. Alzheimer, vascular dementia, Lewy body dementia, and frontotemporal lobe dementia) that affect cognition and may lead to mental degradation. All types of dementia are observed to be chronic and progressive.

We performed a literature review of prognostic dementia risk models and identified common drawbacks to be relatively small sample sizes, a limited set of manually selected predictors, as well as reliance on non-routinely collected information (e.g. years of education, pesticide exposure). In addition, prediction is performed across a wide range of age groups, generally specified as *above the age of 65*. We believe these factors may prevent wider adoption of the proposed models.

To overcome this, we aim to predict 5-year dementia risk using routinely collected health data from various databases. Our approach evaluates predictive performance in a real-world setting, without pre-selecting predictors or imputing data.

Methods

We defined several target cohorts by stratifying patients above the age of 60 into 5-year age groups. The index date was defined as the first outpatient visit since entering the age group (before 1 January 2013). As additional inclusion criteria, we require 5 years of follow up time and the absence of a condition occurrence of dementia or other cognitive impairments any time prior. Patients also should not have had a condition occurrence of a disease indicating subtypes of dementia (e.g. Pick's disease, parkinsonism, Huntington's chorea).

Prediction is performed using LASSO logistic regression. We specified a time-at-risk of 5 years and a washout period of 3 years before the index date. Several thousand predictors have been included covering demographics, condition occurrences, drug exposures, procedures performed, measurements, observations, and device exposures. The following table summarizes the study populations across four databases of interest. IBM MDCR is a U.S. claims database that holds patient data of retirees, Iqvia Germany DA comprises patient data of primary care interventions in Germany, Optum databases hold U.S. claims data including lab analyte results and administrative data, as well as socioeconomic information such as ethnicity, income, education, marital status.

Age groups	IBM MDCR		Iqvia Germany DA		Optum Extended SES		Optum Panther	
	Records	Events (4.8%)	Records	Events (1.1%)	Records	Events (2.2%)	Records	Events (1.1%)
60 – 64	15,282	733 (4.8%)	147,815	1,556 (1.1%)	291,563	6325 (2.2%)	1,039,545	11,889 (1.1%)
65 – 69	308,948	13,718 (4.4%)	131,690	3,295 (2.6%)	294,022	12,301 (4.2%)	866,669	21,426 (2.5%)
70 – 74	478,317	29,366 (6.1%)	169,559	8,366 (4.9%)	363,263	26,014 (7.2%)	700,056	36,658 (5.2%)
75 – 79	406,050	50,440 (12.4%)	116,177	11,277 (9.7%)	375,272	59,316 (15.8%)	544,754	57,197 (10.5%)
80 – 84	300,908	67,687 (22.5%)	59,979	11,214 (18.7%)	316,637	96,127 (30.4%)	640,323	148,613 (23.2%)
85 – 89	161,971	60,340 (37.3%)	24,698	7,924 (32.1%)				
90 – 94	55,018	29,841 (54.2%)	5,680	2,731 (48.1%)				
95 – 99	10,907	7,595 (69.6%)						

Results

A prediction model has been developed for each age group within each database. We report discrimination ability using the area under the Receiver Operating Characteristic curve (AUROC) as well as model calibration using the calibration slope.

Age groups	MDCR		Iqvia Germany DA		Optum Extended SES		Optum Panther	
	AUROC	Cal. Slope	AUROC	Cal. Slope	AUROC	Cal. Slope	AUROC	Cal. Slope
60 – 64	0.83	1.22	0.77	1.05	0.77	1.14	0.74	1.16
65 – 69	0.74	1.03	0.75	1.04	0.74	1.05	0.71	1.10
70 – 74	0.74	1.03	0.73	0.91	0.74	1.06	0.69	1.07
75 – 79	0.74	1.03	0.74	1.01	0.73	1.04	0.67	1.03
80 – 84	0.74	1.00	0.73	0.94	0.74	1.00	0.68	1.04
85 – 89	0.74	1.01	0.70	1.02				
90 – 94	0.75	1.00	0.66	0.96				
95 – 99	0.74	1.07						

Preliminary results showed reasonable discrimination performance and calibration, with the MDCR models showing highest average performance and stability across all age groups. By direct comparison to some models in literature, which do not use routinely collected health data (AUROC between 0.73 and 0.89) our model at this point in time underperform slightly. [1-4]

Conclusions

We developed various prediction models using routinely collected health data from four different databases. We believe that our models, which do not rely on manual predictor selection or data imputation and use data commonly available in observational health databases, will be easier to implement and update, which may result in a wider adoption in clinical practice.

By stratifying patients into age groups we observed our models' discrimination performances for Iqvia Germany DA and Optum Panther to decline in older populations. Future work will focus on studying the frequency of variables selected by each model in these different age groups to deepen our understanding of dementia prediction.

Next steps will focus on externally validating the prediction models in the respective other databases as well as further improving model performances.

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Poster 3 ([Link](#))

Development of a R-package to Explore Heterogeneity of Treatment Effects: A Demonstration in Patients with Hypertension

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Background

Heterogeneity of treatment effect (HTE) is the non-random, explainable variability in the direction and magnitude of treatment effects for individuals within a population. The most common approach to HTE assessment is through subgroup analyses where interactions with various covariates are tested. However, detection of such interactions needs much bigger sample sizes than the detection of main effects and RCTs are rarely powered to detect them. Subgrouping patients on a summary score like their predicted risk of the outcome, can act as a remedy and help identify groups of patients more likely to benefit from specific treatment choices.

The OMOP-CDM enables a generalized approach, where multiple outcomes can be considered for a broad range of exposures. In this regard, the Large-scale Evidence Generation in Network of Databases (LEGEND) project generated evidence on the effects of almost all medical interventions for the case of hypertension. We aim to develop an OHDSI analytics package that provides insight into treatment effect heterogeneity. We provide a demonstration for hypertension, comparing ACE inhibitors to Beta blockers with respect to cardiovascular disease (CVD) events and cough events in Truven MarketScan Commercial Claims and Encounters (CCAE) database.

Methods

Cohort	Definition
Treatment (ACE inhibitors)	Hypertensive patients receiving drugs within the ACE inhibitor drug major class.
Comparator (Beta blockers)	Hypertensive patients receiving drugs within the Beta blocker drug major class.
Outcome1 (CVD)	Total cardiovascular disease events (ischemic stroke, hemorrhagic stroke, heart failure, acute myocardial infraction or sudden death).
Outcome2 (Cough)	Cough events.

- Personalized predictions of CVD risk were estimated using LASSO logistic regression on the combined treatment and comparator cohorts.
- Propensity scores were estimated using LASSO logistic regression within quartiles of predicted CVD risk.
- Covariates were balanced using inverse probability of treatment weights.
- Relative risks of CVD events were estimated using weighted Cox proportional hazards regression within quartiles of predicted CVD risk.
- Absolute risk reduction in CVD risk was estimated using the difference of the weighted Kaplan-Meier estimators within quartiles of predicted CVD risk

- Relative and absolute risk differences of cough events within quartiles of predicted CVD risk were made in the same way as above.

Results

CVD hazard ratios are quite constant across quartiles of predicted CVD risk, leading to increasing absolute treatment benefits in favor of ACE inhibitors. There appears to be increased cough risk for patients receiving ACE inhibitors. However, absolute cough risk does not increase with CVD risk, encouraging the use of ACE inhibitors for high CVD risk patients.

Conclusions

We are developing an R-package that performs treatment comparisons within strata of predicted outcome risks. We intend to use this package to incorporate treatment effect heterogeneity assessment to the results of the LEGEND project, with regard to hypertension treatment. The under development RiskStratifiedEstimation package can be found at: <https://github.com/OHDSI/RiskStratifiedEstimation>.

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Poster 4 ([Link](#))

How much data do we need for clinical prediction?

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Background

Historically, clinical prediction models have been developed with limited sample size and relatively few predictor variables [1]. In recent years, however, large observational health databases have opened up possibilities to develop clinical prediction models at a much larger scale, for a host of target populations and health outcomes and using large sample sizes [2].

To take advantage of the predictive power of such data sources the Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics (OHDSI) initiative has designed and implemented a prediction framework for observational health data standardized to a common data model [3]. This framework can be used to develop and validate clinical prediction models across disparate observational health databases, for example from administrative claims and electronic health records, effectively enabling the development of models at a global scale.

Objective

It is unknown whether these large amounts of observational health data help to improve model performance or unnecessarily put constraints on computing resources and computation time. Constraining large datasets based on an optimal sample size may facilitate the development of clinical prediction models at scale.

In this retrospective study we investigate sample size requirements for developing clinical prediction models using routinely collected observational health data. We empirically assess the effect of sample size on discrimination performance (AUROC) by generating learning curves for a diverse set of clinical prediction problems. We also compare our results to the popular 10 Events Per Variable (EPV) rule, which can be used to estimate an optimal sample size.

Figure 1. Patient-level prediction as defined by OHDSI.

Methods

We define *patient-level prediction* as a modeling process wherein a *health outcome* is predicted within a *time-at-risk* period relative to a *target cohort* start date (Figure 1). Prediction is performed using a set of predictors derived from patient data in an observation window prior to the start of the target cohort. The prediction algorithm of choice is logistic regression with L2 regularization (LASSO), which also performs automatic variable selection.

We empirically assess the effect of sample size on prediction performance by generating learning curves for 81 prediction problems of which 23 originated from the patient-level prediction framework study in patients with depression. The remaining 58 prediction problems were defined in patients with hypertension as part of the LEGEND study.

The analysis is performed on multiple data sources.

- IBM® MarketScan® Commercial Database (CAAE)
- IBM® MarketScan® Multi-State Medicaid Database (MDCD)
- IBM® MarketScan® Medicare Supplemental Database (MDCR)

Results

Learning curves show the effect of sample size on discrimination performance (AUROC). We observe diminishing performance returns as we add more data to a model. We also observe that in our highly imbalanced data sets the learning is strongly correlated to the number of outcome events (positive cases) rather than the absolute sample size. Figure 2 shows the learning curves plateauing with 5,000 to 20,000 outcome events. Interestingly, the effect is the same across all three databases

Figure 2. Learning curves generated using Logistic Regression and color coded by database.

Discussion

To make recommendations on the optimal sample size we can empirically estimate the required number of outcome events as a function of the expected performance improvement Δ AUROC (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Optimal sample size as a function of Δ AUROC.

We observed that the automatic variable selection selects more variables as sample size increases. This results in unnecessarily growing model complexity, as discrimination performance can plateau with several thousand outcome events. A model with fewer variables can be transported, applied, and "interpreted" more easily, which outlines the relevance of estimating an optimal number of outcome events using the curve in Figure 3.

Conclusions

We do not need millions of patient records for clinical prediction. An optimal sample size should be defined in terms of the number of outcome events, which agrees with commonly used formulas such as the 10 EPV rule. For iterating over design choices, e.g. finding optimal hyperparameters, one may refer to Figure 3 and choose to use a larger Δ AUROC, while for model deployment a smaller Δ AUROC is recommended.

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Poster 5 ([Link](#))

Assessing heterogeneity of hypertension treatment effects
A risk modeling approach

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Background

- The Large-scale Evidence Generation and Evaluation in a Network of Databases (LEGEND) study compared classes of hypertension drugs for their relative treatment effect on multiple outcomes
- The absolute treatment effect (absolute risk reduction) of one drug class versus another often depends on baseline outcome risk
- We performed a risk-based re-analysis of the LEGEND study, comparing the absolute risk difference of angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitors versus beta blockers for multiple outcomes
- The analyses were performed with regard to baseline 2-year risk of total cardiovascular disease (CVD) risk

Methods

- For our analyses we considered the following databases:
 - IBM MarketScan® Multi-State Medicaid Database (MDCD)
 - IBM MarketScan® Medicare Supplemental Database (MDCR)
 - IBM MarketScan® Commercial Database (CCAE)
- We predicted personalized CVD risk using LASSO logistic regression on the combined ACE-inhibitor and beta blocker cohorts
- We estimated propensity scores using LASSO logistic regression within quartiles of predicted CVD risk
- We used inverse probability of treatment weighting to balance covariates within quartiles of predicted CVD risk
- We estimated absolute risk reduction for each LEGEND outcome from the difference of the weighted treatment-specific (ACE-inhibitors vs beta blockers) Kaplan-Meier estimators within quartiles of predicted CVD risk

Results

Absolute risk reduction estimates (ACE-inhibitors vs beta blockers) for each LEGEND outcome can be found in Figure:

- High CVD risk quartile hypertensive patients (top)
- Low CVD risk quartile hypertensive patients (bottom)

Conclusions

- When comparing ACE inhibitors vs beta blockers:
- Patients at high CVD risk receive substantially more absolute benefit in terms of CVD related outcomes (total CVD, heart failure, arrhythmia) than patients at low CVD risk
 - The magnitude of harms (cough, hyperkalemia) does not increase with CVD risk

CVD risk should be considered when deciding between ACE inhibitors and beta blockers

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